

STUDY OF SOME FACTORS AFFECTING THE THERAPEUTIC EFFICACY OF DRUG FORMS**Bandaliyeva A.***Azerbaijan Medical University,**Department of Pharmaceutical Technology and Management, Senior Lecturer***Huseynova A.***Azerbaijan Medical University,**Department of Pharmaceutical Technology and Management, Senior Lecturer***Aslanov M.***Azerbaijan Medical University, Department of Pharmaceutical Technology and Management,**Senior Lecturer***Mammadli A.***Azerbaijan Medical University, Department of Nutrition and Medical Ecology, Senior Laboratory Assistant***Abstract**

Various therapeutic agents are used for both preventive and therapeutic purposes in maintaining human health, and the quality preparation of these agents is one of the most critical factors. However, many factors influence the therapeutic efficacy of drug forms, and their investigation is a matter of significance. It should be noted that the science of biopharmaceutics deals with understanding the biological reactions related to drugs within the body. In biopharmaceutics, the equivalence of drugs is evaluated chemically, biologically, and therapeutically. After drugs are prepared in a high-quality manner, their substantial positive impact on the human body depends on processes such as absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion. Pharmacokinetics, a subfield of pharmacology, studies these processes. It is essential to emphasize the undeniable role of various factors in the effect of drugs on the body.

The dispensing of medications in pharmacies is accompanied by necessary information from the pharmacist about their administration methods, dosages, dietary regimes, and other rational usage and storage rules. Patients receive information about drug intake from physicians. Unfortunately, in some cases, physicians may provide brief instructions without focusing on specific details of administration, or patients may fail to attach due importance to these details, neglecting the prescribed regimen. Therefore, pharmacists should fill this gap when dispensing medications. Informing patients about drug usage methods is essential to enhance its effectiveness and prevent adverse reactions during treatment.

The irrational use of drugs can significantly reduce their pharmacological effects, irritate the site of administration, and increase their adverse and toxic effects. Considering the numerous environmental factors, the proper use of drugs significantly enhances the effectiveness of pharmacotherapy.

Environmental factors include the complex effects of external conditions (radiation, temperature, atmospheric pressure, humidity, vibration, air and food composition) and internal conditions (physiological, biochemical, and biophysical characteristics), as well as the state of the organism (body weight, age, gender differences, pregnancy, individual sensitivity to certain drugs, heredity, pathological conditions, etc.). Often, the combined influence of internal and external environmental factors leads to changes in both the pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of drugs, thereby increasing or decreasing their efficacy.

Body and environmental temperatures affect physiological and biochemical processes in the body. Radiation energy (gamma rays of radioactive substances, X-rays, ultraviolet and infrared rays in the visible spectrum, and radiation) also impacts the effectiveness of drugs. Thus, pharmacotherapy for patients undergoing radiation therapy should be conducted with greater caution. Overall, a detailed study of the factors influencing the therapeutic efficacy of drug forms is essential and relevant.

Keywords: Biopharmaceutics, Pharmacology, Pharmacokinetics, Therapeutic Efficacy, Drug Form.

In modern medicine, there is no field where medicinal drugs and pharmaceutical agents are not used. Medicinal drugs are the most powerful tools in combating various diseases. They are essential not only for treating diseases but also for implementing preventive measures. Medicinal agents (*Medicamentum*) refer to substances with chemical or physicochemical properties that are used in the treatment, prevention, and diagnosis of diseases. These substances can have various origins, most of which were initially derived from nature. These medicinal agents, known as **Medicamenta cruda**, include raw materials of plant, animal, and mineral origin that have undergone only initial processing.

The creation of these therapeutic agents, the search for their sources, and their utilization as medi-

cal products have always been relevant issues. Innovations in the industrial production of medicines, their development using modern equipment, and a robust scientific research base have enabled the identification of cases where medicines, which are entirely in line with pharmacopeial standards and other specifications but differ in manufacturing methods or excipients, exhibit varying therapeutic effects despite containing the same active ingredient in equivalent amounts.

The phenomenon of therapeutic non-equivalence of drugs, experimentally and clinically confirmed, was so unexpected and uncharacteristic for the traditional pharmaceutical concept that it remained unexplained for a long time. This phenomenon marked the beginning of a *de facto* crisis in the prevailing pharmaceutical doctrine, which was largely based on a commodity-

based approach to small-scale drug production and quality assessment without considering their therapeutic significance.

The main shortcoming of the traditional pharmaceutical doctrine was its perception of drug forms as a simple mechanical mixture of active and auxiliary substances, with preparation based on the laws of physics and chemistry. These limitations necessitated a comprehensive reassessment of the existing pharmaceutical heritage based on the achievements of scientific and technical progress. The pharmaceutical industry, which had achieved a new theoretical outlook treating drugs as the products of complex technological processes, demanded the establishment of a robust scientific base and the incorporation of cutting-edge analytical methods into the practical pharmaceutical manufacturing process—from obtaining the active substance to the preparation and storage of the final drug.

The new biopharmaceutical concept, based solely on precise scientific experience, succeeded in explaining the effects of pharmaceutical operations and processes on the therapeutic efficacy of drugs. It substantiated the medical value of pharmaceutical (technological) factors. Thus, the therapeutic non-equivalence of drugs with the same composition but produced by different companies is now explained not by "individual organism characteristics," "psychological," or "advertising effects," but by variations in their bioefficacy due to variable pharmaceutical factors.

Factors such as the physical and chemical properties of drug substances, biological availability, drug form types, the impact of auxiliary substances and technological processes, as well as external environmental factors, the age, gender, and general condition of individuals, play a significant role in influencing the effects of drugs on the organism. Therefore, a thorough analysis and study of the factors affecting the pharmacotherapeutic efficacy of drugs is crucial.

It should be noted that the science of biopharmaceutics studies the nature of biological reactions related to drugs in the body. In biopharmaceutics, drug equivalence is evaluated chemically, biologically, and therapeutically. After high-quality preparation, the substantial positive effects of drugs on the human body depend on the processes of absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion.

Pharmacokinetics, a subfield of pharmacology, focuses on studying these processes in detail, including absorption, distribution, metabolism (biotransformation), and elimination (excretion). It is an essential and critical medical field that has made it possible to identify biopharmaceutical issues arising in the body in relation to drugs through precise research.

Modern reforms in the pharmaceutical field worldwide exemplify the growing attention and interest in this area. It is important to note that the foundation of pharmaceutical services lies in the creation of a system for the production and supply of high-quality medicines. To provide the population with quality pharmaceutical services, it is extremely important and relevant to conduct accurate biopharmaceutical and pharmacokinetic studies of drugs.

The dispensing of medicines from pharmacies is accompanied by necessary information from the pharmacist about their administration methods, dosages, dietary regimes, and other rational usage and storage rules. Patients generally receive information about drug use from physicians. Unfortunately, in some cases, physicians may provide brief instructions without focusing on specific administration details, or patients may neglect the prescribed regimen, failing to recognize its importance. Therefore, pharmacists must fill this gap when dispensing medications.

The necessity of informing patients about drug usage methods arises from the dual aim of enhancing drug efficacy and preventing adverse reactions during treatment.

The irrational use of medication can significantly reduce its pharmacological effect, irritate the site of application, and increase its adverse and toxic effects. At the same time, considering the impact of numerous environmental factors, the proper administration of pharmaceutical drugs can significantly enhance the effectiveness of pharmacotherapy.

Environmental factors refer to the combined influence of external (radiation, temperature, atmospheric pressure, humidity, vibration, air and food composition) and internal (physiological, biochemical, and biophysical characteristics) environments, as well as the organism's condition (body mass, age, gender differences, pregnancy, individual sensitivity to certain drugs, heredity, pathological conditions, etc.). Often, the combined effect of internal and external environmental factors leads to changes in both the pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of a drug, thereby increasing or decreasing its effectiveness.

The temperature of the body and the environment affects the physiological and biochemical processes within the organism. When the temperature increases, the absorption and transportation of drug substances occur more rapidly, whereas lower temperatures delay these processes. For this reason, localized cooling of body tissues is applied when it is necessary to delay absorption, for instance, during the local application of medications or in cases of bee or snake bites. In clinical practice, the influence of temperature on drug pharmacodynamics must be considered, especially when prescribing medications to patients with acute thermoregulation disorders under various temperature conditions. For example, the use of atropine sulfate in hot weather can negatively impact the body's sweat secretion function, potentially leading to fatal outcomes.

Radiant energy (gamma rays from radioactive substances, X-rays, ultraviolet and infrared rays from the visible spectrum, and radiation) also affects drug efficacy. Under sunlight exposure, the composition of the blood and the effects of substances influencing mineral metabolism may change. After undergoing X-ray therapy, patients may exhibit altered responses to caffeine. Ionizing radiation can alter genetic and metabolic processes as well as the kinetics of drug substances. Consequently, pharmacotherapy for patients undergoing radiation therapy should be conducted with greater caution. It is not advisable to expose the body to intense sunlight when taking medications such as aminazine and other phenothiazines, salicylamides (particularly

for men over 50 years of age), eelenium, diphenhydramine, sulfanilamides, tetracyclines, and nevigramon.

Magnetic fields significantly influence the central nervous system and humoral regulation centers, the bioelectrical activity of the heart and brain, and the permeability of biological membranes. As the energy and

duration of magnetic field exposure increase, the responsiveness of various organs to mediators such as adrenaline and acetylcholine also intensifies. Men are generally more sensitive to the activity of the Earth's magnetic field compared to women.

Patients with nervous and cardiovascular system disorders are particularly sensitive to magnetic storms in the Earth's atmosphere. During magnetic storm days, they may experience disease exacerbations, crises, arrhythmias, angina attacks, decreased work capacity, and other issues. It is recommended to increase the dosage of medications (under a doctor's supervision), use valerian, motherwort, and hawthorn preparations, reduce physical exertion, and avoid stressful situations on such days. Alcohol consumption and smoking are strictly prohibited.

Meteorological factors (such as relative humidity, atmospheric pressure, wind direction and strength, average daily temperature, etc.) influence the elasticity of blood vessels, blood viscosity, and clotting. A drop in atmospheric pressure by 10-12 mmHg can affect vascular conditions, while increased barometric pressure primarily impacts the joints. Rainy weather often leads to depression. Storms and hurricanes have particularly negative effects on human health. Typically, 1 cm³ of air contains 200-1000 positive and negative ions, which affect heart activity, respiration, blood pressure, and metabolism. A high concentration of positive ions can cause depression, shortness of breath, dizziness, reduced overall tone, fatigue, and fainting. In contrast, a high concentration of negative ions has a positive effect on the body, improving mental state and mood. This is thought to occur because negative ions inhibit the production of serotonin, a neurotransmitter associated with

pain sensation. During storms, the amount of negative ions in the atmosphere increases.

The effects of medications also change under hypo- and hyperbaric conditions. Experiments on animals have shown that prolonged exposure to high-altitude regions (3,200 meters above sea level) increases the hypotensive effect of papaverine while reducing that of dibazol. Differences in sensitivity to drugs are linked to genetic factors and the unequal intensity of their metabolism. Therefore, when prescribing and administering medications, it is essential to consider the influence of both internal and external environmental factors.

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